

Human Resurrection

Levels of Difficulty

(Extended)

Abstract: The concept outlined here presents three distinct levels of difficulty concerning the potential achievement of human resurrection based on scientific and technological advancements. Each level proposes different targets and timeframes for achieving this complex feat.

Level 1:

Period: Within 3 centuries

Target: Your DNA

Difficulty Level: Medium

Description: This level involves using the information contained within the DNA of a deceased individual to reconstruct them. Utilizing the genetic information encoded in the DNA, the aim is to reconstruct the person who has passed away. This approach assumes that DNA holds sufficient information to recreate an individual from start to finish.

Level 2:

Period: Within 4-5 centuries

Target: DNA of your successors (children, grandchildren, etc.)

Difficulty Level: Advanced

Description: In this level, the focus shifts to the DNA of the deceased person's descendants, such as their children or grandchildren. It acknowledges the passing down of genetic material through generations, suggesting that the DNA of successors retains information about the deceased individual. The challenge here lies in accessing and interpreting this inherited genetic information.

Level 3:

Period: Within 1 millennium

Target: Random particles in the Universe

Difficulty Level: Very Advanced

Description: This level represents the most challenging and ambitious approach. It proposes using the information present in any particle throughout the Universe. It suggests that particles communicate with each other within a vast network, and these particles contain infinite information, including information about the deceased individual. The concept assumes that every particle possesses comprehensive information about all other particles in the Universe.

Conclusion: These levels outline increasingly complex and ambitious strategies for achieving human resurrection, from utilizing specific DNA information to accessing information present in particles scattered throughout the Universe. The difficulty levels rise significantly with each level, reflecting the challenges associated with the scope and understanding required for such endeavors. Each level presents its unique scientific and technological hurdles to overcome in pursuit of this ambitious goal of human resurrection.

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